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How an Apprenticeship Can Direct Learners Beyond the Local Context of Teaching and Learning: Transferable Skills in Germany's Dual System of Vocational Education

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Abstract

Prior research showed that trainees/apprentices in the German dual system (DS) acquire what can be termed transferable skills, such as being able to assess when more information is needed and how to get it. This paper draws on the British educational sociologist Basil Bernstein and his code theory to approach the question of how these learners acquire such skills. Embedded in Bernstein's code is an orientation to meanings, which in formal education is elaborated, that is, it takes learners beyond a narrowly localised orientation. The paper argues that an elaborated orientation, first indications for which in the DS were found in prior research, is a necessary precondition also for skills transfer. A *Beruf*, a Germanic conceptualisation of occupation and one of the DS's organisational principles, can be regarded as a discourse in Bernstein's sense. With Bernstein, the paper argues that a boundary principle within *Beruf* education, which is established by the social partners, concerns not only sites, but also knowledge, agents and discourse, and can be encountered also at the micro-level of transmission. The paper's empirical part draws on retrospective problem-centred interviews with graduates to illustrate learners' experiences of boundaries in the DS. Respondents spoke of medium strong boundaries (school and company knowledge complementing each other) or even very strong boundaries (no relation or even contradiction between *Beruf*-school knowledge and company knowledge). However, respondents used the different knowledges productively, to the effect that they acquired the transferable skill of being able to assess when more information is needed and how to get it. Moreover, respondents were able to see the different knowledges as socially created and positioned and to relate them to the overarching *Beruf* discourse. In conclusion, the paper points to the relevance of the discursive regulation of company learning by *Beruf* for the development of elaborated orientations and a disposition for skills transfer.

Keywords

skills transfer, social structuring of VET, Basil Bernstein, dual System of VET, Germany

1 Introduction

This paper investigates the conditions for the acquisition of transferable skills in Germany's dual system (DS) of vocational education and training (VET), a form of education which enjoys high reputation among employers, learners and researchers alike. Nägele and Stalder (2017; henceforth: N+S) explain that transferable skills, technical and non-technical, are “much sought after by employers” and “can be used to act efficiently in different real-life situations” (op. cit., p.739). Yet in the DS, the first transmission site is the training company, and “Critical voices have sometimes argued that the skills acquired through vocational and professional education and training are too narrow and only related to very specific tasks and situations, resulting in skills which are not transferable” (op.cit., p.746). Some authors (e.g., Wheelahan, 2010) pointed to the obligatory VET-school complementing workplace learning, where trainees/apprentices would learn necessary abstract (and, therefore, transferable) theoretical knowledge. N+S (2017, p. 747) concur: “When theory and practice fall together, a learner gets captured by the task, and an orientation towards understanding the learning content, as opposed to simply reproducing the material, occurs”.

A corollary to this assumption would be to advance the collaboration of learning venues (VET-school and company). However, Gessler (2017) noted a decreasing interest in the cooperation between schools and companies over the past 20 years. Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia (2005, [24], author's translation) showed that collaboration occurs “only in individual cases, without generalisable character”, as “voluntary acts within the professional activities of agents”. Gessler (2017, p. 189f; author's translation) found that the German DS “shows a high degree of institutionalised collaboration on the macro-level and on the exo-level. The in-company training and the school-based learning on the meso-level however, are, in contrast, loosely coupled”, so that the DS “is working also without collaboration between companies and vocational schools”. Yet there is evidence that young people do acquire transferable skills in the DS (cf. Dorau et al., 2009), such as: assessing when further information is needed and how to get it, assessing how long it takes to do a job, making decisions under conditions of uncertainty, self-confidence, and others. To approach Gessler's puzzle, and to relate Dorau's findings to the social structuring of Germany's DS, concepts are required that are able to translate macro into micro and micro into macro – as does the conceptual language developed by the British educational sociologist Basil Bernstein. Drawing on these concepts, this paper suggests that the very boundary between VET school and company in the DS fosters the practicing of boundary crossing and, thereby, a disposition for skills transfer.

For trainees/apprentices, skills transfer implies mental boundary crossing. Bernstein's code theory conceptualises boundaries as classifications. His famous code is a function of classifications and framings (interaction within these boundaries). Embedded into Bernstein's code is an orientation to meanings, which ranges between restricted (implicit, localised, context-dependent) and elaborated (explicit, abstract, context-independent). Elaborated orientations (EOs) make learners see that things can be thought of or done in different ways, depending, for instance, on contextual factors. EOs index learners' disposition for boundary crossing and skills transfer.

Whatever skills are to be transferred, and there is no definite list of transferable skills (N+S, 2017, p. 746), Nägele and Stalder (ibid.) state that pre-conditions for skills transfer are the safety that may arise from an occupational identity, self-confidence and a feeling of being competent. Bernstein (1990, p. 62) concurs with N+S when he postulates a feeling of safety as a necessary precondition for the acquisition of elaborated orientations. He also concurs with N+S about the absence of a list of transferable skills: “Bernstein is very definite that code-regulated consciousness cannot be investigated piecemeal, concept by concept, word by word, fragment by fragment of activity” (Hasan, 2004, p. 40) nor, one may add, skill by skill. Bernstein's elaborated orientation, an orientation beyond the local context, links with the concept of

disposition for skills transfer. But instead of seeking a definite list of transferable skills to be included in curricula, Bernstein's theory widens the perspective to the structural conditions of teaching and learning, which can or cannot become a practice field for learners' skills transfer.

After an introduction to theoretical concepts, this paper investigates, on the basis of problem-centred interviews with DS graduates, classifications (boundaries) within the dual system. Exemplary interview quotations reveal that these boundaries challenged respondents to navigate between contexts and to make meaning of different knowledges and skills they were expected to acquire, of different texts they were expected to produce. The paper shows that trainees/apprentices were able to bring together what they learnt at the VET-school and at the company, that they were able to see knowledge as socially created and positioned, which indexes an elaborated orientation. Successful dealing with boundaries within education should foster feelings of safety, self-confidence and competence that are necessary also to cross boundaries and to transfer knowledge and skills to new contexts later in life.

2 Bernstein's theory

Embedded into Bernstein's famous "code", which is defined as a function of classification (boundaries) and framing (interaction within these boundaries), is an orientation to meanings, which can be restricted (localised, intimate) or elaborated (abstract, context-independent). The elaborated orientation (henceforth briefly: EO) takes learners beyond themselves and beyond a narrow orientation they may bring with them. Institutionalised education is always predicated on the transmission of EOs (Bernstein 1990, p. 40). EOs are the "media for thinking the 'unthinkable', the 'impossible'"; they "go beyond local space, time, context and embed and relate the latter to a transcendental space, time, context" (Bernstein, 1990, p. 182). Bernstein's definition of EOs is based on the assumption that, in realist and Bernsteinian terms, knowledge is socially produced and "has as its object the independently existing generative structures of the natural and social realms" (Moore, 1984, p. 185). An understanding of the practices of knowledge production as "practices positioned within the social relations of generative structures" (Moore, 1984, p. 185), "is a necessary (though by no means sufficient) condition for the intentional transformation of social relations" (ibid.). "The development of elaborated orientations through education invariably occurs where individuals are directed towards new sets of unfamiliar positioned-practices so that it is the practices not the positions which become the object" (Moore, 1984, p. 412; emphases original). Potentially such an understanding of knowledge and the practices of its production can even transform learners from mechanical reproducers of knowledge to producers of new (not only for themselves) knowledge. Presumably, it can also predispose learners towards the application of old (for them) knowledge to new contexts, that is, towards knowledge and skills transfer.

Realisations of the (elaborated) meanings in education, how they are legitimately to be made public, are "a function of the specific form taken by the interactional practices of education" (Bernstein, 1990, p. 32). Central features for the analysis of interactional practices are a category relation and its message (ibid). The relation between categories is a "classificatory principle, which, in turn, is regulated by the social division of labour constituted by a given distribution of power" (ibid.). Put differently, the macro-social distribution of power establishes a classificatory principle which learners (and also transmitters) experience as the boundaries of the pedagogic communicative practice at the transmission level (classroom or equivalent, such as a workplace in a training company), boundaries of what may legitimately be put together and how that is to be made public. In Bernstein's words: "The principle of the internal and external classification of the pedagogic context is invisibly present in any communicative realization of the context" (Bernstein, 1990, p. 37). The principle of classification, thus, provides an answer to Gessler's (2017) puzzle that the dual system implies

coordination of learning sites at the macro-level, but apparent loose coupling at the micro-level of transmission – the classificatory principle should be present at all levels.

So far, nothing has been said about the categories to be classified. Gessler (2017) pointed to sites and categories of transmitters (*Beruf* school teacher and company trainer) as indexing a boundary (classification). Bernstein widens this perspective theoretically. “Classification refers to the degree of insulations between categories of discourse, agents, practices, contexts” (Bernstein, 1990, p. 214). In other words, Bernstein makes researchers aware that boundaries within education, which may become a practice field for learners’ boundary crossing and skills transfer, concern not only agents, but also contexts, knowledge, discourse. “In the analysis of relations between categories (subjects, spaces, discourses), classification refers to the degree of maintenance of boundaries between those categories; it is strong when there is a marked boundary between categories and it is weak when there is a blurring of boundaries between categories” (Morais and Neves, 2018). Moreover, classifications can have internal and external values, depending on whether the boundary is maintained from outside or from within. Strong internal classifications foster a strong feeling of identity (which, according to N+S (p. 746), is supportive for skills transfer). To state in a non-circular way, whether a boundary between particular categories is strong or weak, indicators are required by which the boundary strength comes to show. These have to be developed from the data.

Framing, the other element of Bernstein’s code, is about the locus of control over the interaction within the boundaries and can likewise have stronger or weaker values, depending on the degree of participation that the dominant interaction partner grants the weaker partner. Prior research about the framing relations in Germany’s Dual system (DS) showed that these can be very weak, to the extent that trainees/apprentices can and do take control over the what and how of pedagogic communication, and also over the hierarchy in the transmitter-acquirer-relationship (Höhns, 2018, 2022). In schools, this would be termed illegitimate. Yet these empirical findings, which are based on systematic and rule-related Bernsteinian analyses, made sense when the DS was seen as a real-life example for Moore’s (1984) Bernstein-based oppositional (to schooling) model of an elaborated form of education (cf. Höhns, 2022). These findings make the DS’s underlying classificatory principle an all the more interesting object of investigation.

Höhns (2016, p. 208) argued that a *Beruf* is a discourse in Bernstein’s sense, “insofar as the bundling of texts or work activities produced in a primary context is the product of the social division of labour of certain agents/agencies and of their corresponding social relations”. The social partners create the *Beruf* discourse, and concurrently they create the curriculum for company transmission (the training regulations). They also support the *Beruf*-schools to adapt their curricula when a *Beruf* changes (cf., e.g., Kuppe et al., 2014). The *Beruf*-schools in Germany, like the training companies, are subjected to the same *Beruf* discourse. For the trainee/apprentice, the school is a context beyond the training company, yet equally related to *Beruf* learning, just as are optional other transmission contexts, such as inter-company training sites. It follows that the DS’s intra-discourse relations, which learners experience in their traineeship/apprenticeship, imply a classification (insulation) of sites or transmission contexts, and consequently of categories of agents (e.g., VET school teachers and company trainers). Yet the overarching discourse is the *Beruf*.

Trainees/apprentices are left to their own devices to bring together their experiences at different sites and with different agents within *Beruf*-education. The following section shows that trainees/apprentices are able to make sense of these experiences, even contradictory ones, and to recognise and realise different context-specific productions. In Bernstein’s terms, they learn to see knowledges and practices as differentially positioned and, thereby, develop an elaborated orientation, beyond the context of the training company.

3 Empirical part: The German dual system of VET – boundaries

Knowledgeable informants on transferable skills are persons whose labour market entry trajectory could be termed ‘non-linear’ (e.g., frequent changes of employment, disappearance from the labour market statistics, employment in positions not related to the acquired *Beruf* (occupation)). By this criterion DS graduates were selected from a 2% random sample of all employed persons in Germany to narrate about their vocational education and life before and after in problem-centred interviews (cf. Witzel and Reiter, 2012). Problem-centred means open interviews with some guidance to keep narrations focussed on a socially structured problem, such as, here, vocational learning. From a first set (10 interviews), a content analysis uncovered what remained of the vocational training after such significant career changes and what can be termed transferable skills (cf. Dorau et al., 2009): assessing when further information is needed and how to get it, assessing how long it takes to do a job, making decisions under conditions of uncertainty, self-confidence, and others. Respondents claimed to have acquired these skills (in a very broad sense of the word) during their vocational training and found them useful even when not working in the acquired *Beruf*. This paper analyses a second set of 30 respondents drawn by the same criteria from an improved data base that also included unemployed persons. The interviews were recorded, transcribed, anonymised and fed into a text analysis programme. They were coded with theoretical codes, drawn from Bernstein’s theory, such as: Agents, Sites, Discourse. The code “Agents” received subcodes: Trainers, Colleagues, VET school teachers, Other trainees/apprentices. The code “Sites” received subcodes: Company, VET school, Inter-company training. The code “Discourse” received subcodes: Knowledge, Relation between VET-school and company, Relation between theory and practice. Multiple codings are possible. Quotations are recognisable unambiguously by the interview ID and transcript line number. The interviews were carried out in German and excerpts translated by this paper’s author. The paper draws mainly on the codes: discourse, and sites.

Theoretically, an index for a weak boundary between VET school and company practice is when, as N+S (2017, p. 747) propose, theory and practice fall together. No examples for this were found in the data. When theory and practice have got nothing in common, this indexes a strong boundary. Knowledges complementing each other, indexes a medium strong (permeable) boundary.

Examples for the school (or other sites) complementing company learning:

“Sometimes they [the journeymen] asked whether we had done that in school already... And then one said either yes or no, and then, sometimes, when one did not know, he showed, and sometimes he said: ‘Oh, then I rather do it myself’” (7467405 roofer (m), line 88).

“We had inter-company training at the guild... In the first two courses you learn safety training, that was key... And then we learnt how the training course is structured... How the training plan comes about, and so on. Nothing that would get us anywhere. But the information was necessary to understand why, for instance, the superior reacts the way he does” (8300807 electronics engineer (m), lines 65 and 438).

“In the second year, we had a course on machines... organised by the guild, I think... There they show you, during one week, the functioning of machines. How to operate them, how to set up what, and so on. And then one did that in the carpentry on one’s own. You got a task, ‘There, this piece of wood has to be processed like - such and such. Do that.’ And then you stood at the machines and processed the wood” (ID 8306158 carpenter (f), line 126).

A lawyer’s assistant (8304481 (f), line 191), who had a training place not in a lawyer’s office, but in the legal department of a big company, needed the *Beruf*-school to learn *beruf*-related knowledges that did not occur in the company: “... for instance the calculation of lawyer’s fees. We did not have that in the company...”.

On the other hand, the company complemented the school. The lawyer's assistant (8304481, line 193) continued: "Then, questions arose, and he [the company trainer, a lawyer; author's addition] always gave examples and helped me, explained things."

Specialist (f) in the hotel business (8304172, line 235): "We could go [to the head of the banquet section; author's addition] and say, 'here, we are having wine at school, and I have no idea. We do wine testing at school, and somehow, I have no idea'. Then she said: 'Well, come on, then we shall do something like that here'".

Carpenter (8306158, (f), lines 178-184): "Starting from the first week, the relation to my journeyman was very good. When I had problems at school, or questions, when I had not understood something at school, I went up to him, and he explained it. That was no problem at all... Without him, surely, I would not have passed the examination..." Interviewer: "Did you prepare for the examination together with him?" Respondent: "That would be an exaggeration to say. I am a person who likes to learn on her own. But when there are questions, and they can explain only poorly at school, then you go to him, and he explains it better. Because in the school, they have only their standard shibboleths, and that's it. Because they are all only theoreticians. But he is a practician, he knows what I am talking about. Therefore, he can explain differently, and you understand it" (8306158 carpenter (f), lines 178-184).

In sum, medium-strong classification means that the school, to some extent, compensates deficiencies in training companies concerning the complete *Beruf*-knowledge, and company trainers compensate the school's deficiencies concerning, for instance, practice/rehearsing and explanations. In order to receive these explanations from their trainers, trainees/apprentices have to be able to ask for them in a contextually adequate way. To know how to get information, when needed, is one of the transferable skills identified in prior research (Dorau et al., 2009). Obviously, trainees/apprentices are able to use the divergences between company and *Beruf*-school productively – as a practice field for the acquisition of an important transferable skill.

Respondents also spoke about contradictions between VET school and company (very strong classification). The shortest, but telling response on a question about the interplay between school and hotel, theory and practice, was a laugh (25087338 specialist (f) in the hotel business, lines 327ff). Interviewer: "You laugh..." Respondent: "Yes, because, theory is theory and practice is practice, you cannot implement that. The teachers teach us things that don't exist any more... I remember a special glass for *Knickebein* [a liqueur cocktail; author's addition]..., it is not produced any more. But we nevertheless had to learn, what it is for. Or certain things that are not realisable in practice... Certain points, how one should theoretically proceed, are impossible in practice, because there is not the time to think three times in advance and make a plan how to organise an event... I think it [the curriculum] should generally be overhauled, particularly nowadays..." Interviewer: "That is, you did not find anything in common, but everything very different?" Respondent: "Well, in parts yes, but in parts not at all. Actually, there is opposition. But the teachers said that, too, like: 'Theoretically you have to learn it like that and be able to do like that, but in practice that's not possible'" (25087338 specialist (f) in the hotel business).

Another specialist (f) in the hotel business (8304172, line 351) explained: "I can understand that there are guidelines, how to do things. But I can also understand that in practice, in this day-to-day business, you cannot do it like that, because it takes too much. Sometimes that was a problem. For instance, in a practice lesson at school, we had... to lay a table, and then one trainee did it like this and another one like that. There was a big discussion about where the glasses should stand. In the beginning, before we really knew where things really go... Some trainees, indeed, did not put red wine and white wine glasses on the table at all, but just water glasses. Or they put things in other places... At some point one had to clarify for oneself: OK, here I have to draw a line. Where does this belong for the examination, how do I have to do this for the examination. And THAT is how the company wants it, because it is easier or, maybe,

not every hotel in Germany has got special cutlery for dessert or for fish. After all, in one school class, people come from different companies... And then one had to say OK, the school wants it like this, and this is right for the examination. One could try at a quiet moment in the company to do it like this [like the school suggests; author's addition], but what, if it did not fit, when so and so many people had to be seated on the bench, and one could not put the second glass on the table.... Well, that's how it really was (laughing).... Yes, there are differences between what you learn and what you do in the company. But I think, that's the case in every *Beruf*, no matter which one, it will always be different (laughing)".

A dental technician (8200101 (m), lines 140ff) also spoke about the fundamental difference between *Beruf*-school knowledge and labour practice. Interviewer: "You just mentioned the *Beruf*-school, and you remarked straight away that you saw theory and practice diverging... Could you elaborate that a little further...?" Respondent: "Well, cost accounts, costings which are not realisable, ideas about labour time, labour protection, if you stick to what you learn at school, the job is not doable. That's not just a little bit you have to give up, but it is impossible to work the way you learn it at school. Well, but I think, that's the same in most occupations. At least, sure, you talk with your mates, who work in other jobs, and - I think it's the same everywhere, that one does not stick so much to this theory, as it is taught ideally".

In sum, contradictions between school knowledge and practice knowledge make learners recognise the context-boundedness (and time-boundedness; cf. the out-dated *Knickebein* glass) of knowledge. Things can be done and thought of in different ways. The respondents also gave reasons, why they considered school knowledge as not applicable in practice: time restrictions, different spatial and material conditions, too costly.

Respondents were also able to see the overarching *Beruf* discourse, as the following narration of a Bank clerk (f) (8306138, line 367ff) illustrates. Interviewer: "Was there coordination between what you learnt in the *Beruf*-school and what you learn in the company?" Respondent: "There was no temporal connexion. Actually, there was complete separation... One thing was school, the other thing was company." Interviewer: "But you did not mind much." Respondent: "No..., no...At some stage it all comes together. No later than at the end of the traineeship. (laughs)". In other words, the respondent unproblematically accepted the school knowledge and the company knowledge as both belonging to *Beruf* knowledge. Against researchers such as N+S (2017, p. 747), who propose that theory and practice should fall together, respondents did not worry about a mismatch between theory and practice, but were able to see and accept knowledge as socially created and positioned. This ability, which is also a necessary precondition for, in Bernstein's terms, an elaborated orientation, is certainly helpful also for later skills transfer.

4 Conclusions

The paper argued that an elaborated orientation in Bernstein's sense is an important precondition for skills transfer, and that this orientation implies the ability to see knowledge as socially created and positioned. An elaborated orientation is embedded into Bernstein's code, which is a function of classification (boundaries) and framing (interaction). The paper investigated boundaries (classifications) in the dual system's intra-discourse relations concerning different learning spaces: the training company, the *Beruf*-school and the inter-company training sites. Learners who are able to deal productively with such boundaries within *Beruf*-education, should possess a disposition also for later skills transfer.

Narrations from interviews with DS graduates showed that respondents perceived the knowledge transmitted at each of the sites as context-related and discourse-related. Respondents were also able to see that *Beruf*-school knowledge (and knowledge obtained in other transmission sites such as inter-company training sites) complements learning in the company, and vice versa, to make the complete *Beruf*-knowledge. In the *Beruf*-school, the

respondents also saw the advantages and limitations of their company as a learning place for the whole of the *Beruf*. Narrations revealed the respondents' ability, in a contextually adequate way, to make trainers explain what reached beyond the everyday practice in the company but what they needed to know in the *Beruf*-school and for the complete *Beruf*. That is, trainees/apprentices took responsibility for their *Beruf*-learning and concurrently acquired a transferable skill (assessing when further information is needed and how to get it). They also saw the limitations of *Beruf*-school knowledge and were able to reason why the theoretical knowledge is not really applicable: time restrictions, different spatial and material conditions, costs. Respondents who saw knowledge in the company and in the school as socially created and positioned, developed, in Bernstein's terms, an elaborated orientation, which directed them beyond a narrow, localised orientation of learning to work in a particular company.

Bernstein's conceptual language permitted this paper to relate individual narrations to underlying structures, and the organisational form of transmission/acquisition to the acquisition of a transferable skill. Bernstein's theory widens the perspective of transferable skills to the structural conditions of teaching and learning, which can become a practice field for learners' skills transfer. The overarching discursive construct *Beruf*, which comprises more than what is required to work in the training company, seems to play a crucial role here.

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Biographical note

Gabriela Höhns retired in 2022. During her work as researcher in the Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training, she developed a special interest in educational sociology and, in particular, in Basil Bernstein's code theory. She published Bernstein-based analyses of different aspects of Germany's Dual System. She is a member of the Educational Research section of the German Sociological Association.